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MENTALITY AND NATIONALITY IN PROVERBS OF ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article under study aims at investigating the semantics and pragmatics of the English, Russian and Uzbek proverbs from the point of view on lingo-cultural aspects. To reach the goal the researchers applied such methods of investigation as descriptive method, oppositional analysis of the English, Russian and Uzbek proverbs, method of comparative analyses, statistical method, method of generalization.

Language has a great impact on the culture of a nation and reflects mentality, cultural heritage and lifestyle of people from the past till now. Language units such as aphorisms, phraseological units, idioms and others show wisdom and outlook of the nation. Especially, proverbs are the mirror of nation's worldview. For this reason, below we will focus on the issues of mentality and national color in the proverbs of the English, Uzbek and Russian languages.

It is well known that proverbs are a valuable material of the language fund. They are invaluable examples of folk art; express the national and cultural characteristics of the people, their worldview and the spirit of the nation. As the famous linguist Dahl said "a collection of proverbs is a collection of proverbs taken from the language of the people, from experience, from common

sense, from the truth that the people have found in life" [2,171]. Dwelling on the proverbs of different languages, we see that they are a reflection of the historical, spiritual and material culture of the people who are native speakers of the same language. Therefore, a comparative study of proverbs of different languages helps to reveal the specific cultural and national aspects of a nation, in other words, to show the mentality of the same people.

Despite the fact that the concept of "mentality" was introduced into the language paradigm not so long ago, it is currently used in a very wide range. In a narrow sense, mentality is used in the context of "the sphere of thinking, the world of outlook", while in a broad sense "morality, education and imagination of the people are understood" [3, 59]. One of V.V.'s linguists. Kolesov puts

the sign of equality between the concepts of "mentality" and "picture of the world", calling it "understanding the world within the framework of the Russian language, combining intellectual, spiritual and volitional properties" [4, 14].

The concept of mentality was introduced by the linguist V. we can also see in the visions of von Humboldt. He believed that the mentality is "the character of the people, reflected not only in their language, but also in literature, religion and other spiritual spheres" [5, 348]. Therefore, as already mentioned, this "national character" is closely linked to the religion, politics, traditions, social stratum, way of life, history, and even geographical location of the people.

Speaking about nationality in English proverbs, it is impossible not to mention the character of the English people. Among the peoples of the world, the representatives of this people are distinguished by pride. This aspect is also evident in proverbs:

Better to reign in hell, Than serve in heaven.

A civil denial is better than a rude grant ("it is better to be rejected with respect than to be rudely rewarded").

We also observe that another aspect common to the English is that their attachment to pets is very high and in the proverbs we can often meet images of "dogs", especially "cats". For example:

Dog does not eat dog.

Barking dogs bite herring.

When the cat is away, the mice will play.

A cat in gloves catches no mice.

Religion is also very important in the national culture. This seems to be more obvious than in Uzbek and Russian proverbs, that is, in them the images of heaven, hell and Satan occupy a large place:

Hell is paved with good intentions

Better to reign in hell, than serve in heaven

The devil is not so black as he is painted
He that sups with the devil should have a long spoon.

Speaking about the concept of mentality in the proverbs of the Uzbek language, it is impossible not to recall the hospitality in the blood of Uzbek people. Respect for the guest, tolerance are evident in our proverbs. For example:

Mehmon – atoyi xudo (A guest is a gift of the God)

Mehmon kelsa eshikdan, rizqi kelar teshikdan (If the guest comes through the door, his subsistence comes through the hole.

At the same time, Uzbeks are children's people, and attention to mother and child is important:

Ona bilan bola – gul bilan lola (A child with his mother – a tulip with a flower)

Bolali uy – bozor, bolasiz uy mozor (A house with children is a market, a house without children is a grave).

Bolamning bolasi – qandin o'rik donasi (My baby's baby – sweet apricot candy)

It should also be recognized that the images "mother-in-law" and "bride" are typical only for Uzbek proverbs. For example:

Kelin bo'ldim - qaynonamga yoqmadim, qaynona bo'ldim - kelinimga yoqmadim (Becoming a daughter-in-law I was not liked by mother-in-law, becoming a mother-in-law I was not liked by the daughter-in-law).

Qaynonaga tosh otsang tosh olasan, qaynonaga osh bersang osh olasan.

If you throw stone to your mother-in-law, you will get a stone, if you give a meal to your mother-in-law, you will get a meal.

Such things as shame, prudence and modesty can be found in Uzbek proverbs. For instance:

The horse of prudence is a coward.

Immodesty is a sign of disgrace.

The Uzbek people honour bread very much, and we can see this in proverbs:

Non mo'lligi - el to'qligi (Abundance of bread – repletion of the nation)

Nonga hurmat – elga hurmat (Respect for bread means respect for the people)

Like other peoples, the Russian nation has its own character. Therefore, national awareness of proverbs is different from other folk proverbs. In them, first of all, you can see the image of the Russian people:

Русский что увидит, то и сделает (A Russian does what he sees)

Русское "ура" грянет - врагу жарко станет (Russian "hurrah" will break out - the enemy will get hot)

Images of Russian cities are also common. For example:

Питер создан миллионами, а Москва – веками (Peter is created by millions, and Moskva-by centuries).

Кто в Москве побывал, тот всю Русь повидал (Whoever has been in Moscow has seen all of Russia).

In addition, geographical location also has an influence on the mentality. As you know, most of Russia is covered by forests, so in proverbs a large place is occupied by images of the "forest" and the wild animals that live in it, especially the "wolf" and "hunter". For example:

Счастье - что волк: обманет да в лес уйдёт (Luck is a wolf: deceives you and go away to the forest).

На ловца (охотника) и зверь бежит (Seeing the hunter the beast will run away).

Волков бояться - в лес не ходить (Who is afraid of wolf will never go to the forest).

At the same time, there are plenty of rivers and seas. Therefore, you can trace the proverbs with the images of "fish" and "seaman":

За чужим столом смелость нужна, как на лодке моряку (Courage is needed at someone else's table, like a sailor on a boat).

Непойманная рыба всегда большой кажется (An uncaught fish always seems big).

Море - наше поле: дает и рыбу, дает и хлеб (the sea is our land: gives fish and bread).

Another image that gives the national flavor to proverbs is national dishes of this country. For example:

In English:

Every cook praises his praises his own broth.

Too many cooks spoil the broth.

In Uzbek:

Har kuni yema palovni, har kuni yoqqil olovni (Don't eat pilaf every day, but burn the fire every day).

Kuningdan bir kuning qolsa ham osh ye (Eat pilaf even if you only have one day left).

In Russian:

Ши да каша - пища наша (Shi and porridge – our food).

Кисель зубов не портит (Kissel does not spoil your teeth).

In short, proverbs are the cultural heritage of people. They reflect all the conjectures, worldview, lifestyle, character and beliefs of the same people. Since each nation has its own characteristics, this has a great influence on its proverbs. Although the themes in the proverbs of different cultures are similar, the images in them are not the same. And these aspects ensure the national colouring of proverbs.

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